

41217 OMAA Abu Dhabi Inter Arprt

SLAT	24.43
SLON	54.65
SELV	27.00
SHOW	1.23
LIFT	2.01
LFTV	1.47
SWET	103.6
KINX	24.10
CTOT	11.30
VTOT	36.30
TOTL	47.60
CAPE	0.00
CAPV	0.02
CINS	0.00
CINV	-671.
EQLV	-9999
EQTV	467.7
LFCT	-9999
LFCV	472.5
BRCH	0.00
BRCV	0.00
LCLT	275.7
LCLP	640.4
LCLE	336.0
MLTH	313.1
MLMR	7.28
THCK	5883.
PWAT	24.32

00Z 05 Sep 2018

University of Wyoming

41217 OMAA Abu Dhabi Inter Arprt

SLAT	24.43
SLON	54.65
SELV	27.00
SHOW	1.20
LIFT	1.28
LFTV	0.61
SWET	103.3
KINX	28.50
CTOT	11.30
VTOT	36.30
TOTL	47.60
CAPE	0.00
CAPV	0.00
CINS	0.00
CINV	0.00
EQLV	-9999
EQTV	-9999
LFCT	-9999
LFCV	-9999
BRCH	0.00
BRCV	0.00
LCLT	272.7
LCLP	584.0
LCLE	338.6
MLTH	318.0
MLMR	6.42
THCK	5894.
PWAT	26.37

12Z 05 Sep 2018

University of Wyoming